

Assessing the spatial optimality of land use and land cover in three European Capitals – implementation a game theory approach

Marek Vach^{a,*}, Kamila Svobodova^{b,c}

^a Faculty of Environmental Sciences, Czech University of Life Sciences Prague, Department of Water Resources and Environmental Modeling, Prague, 16500, Czech Republic

^b Faculty of Environmental Sciences, Czech University of Life Sciences Prague, Department of Landscape and Urban Planning, Prague, 16500, Czech Republic

^c Centre for Social Responsibility in Mining, Sustainable Minerals Institute, The University of Queensland, Saint Lucia, QLD 4072, Australia

* Corresponding author: Marek Vach (vachm@fzp.czu.cz)

Highlights

- We define spatial optimality of land use and land cover (LULC) representation
- Game theory quantifies LULC optimality (LULCO) in Prague, Vienna, Budapest
- Southern Prague boasts high values of LULCO, Budapest follows with a slight decline
- 2012-2018 evaluation reveals urban sustainability impact from LULC changes
- Our method is as general and versatile as the Shannon index but is more sensitive

Abstract

In European cities, the landscape diversity plays a pivotal role in urban sustainability. In this study, we define the local land use and land cover (LULC) optimality (LULCO) as a compromise expressing the maximum relative representation of individual LULC types in a spatial unit. We present the application of a novel game-theoretic method to assess the spatial distribution of the probability of Nash equilibrium expressing the degree of spatial optimality of the representation of forest, pasture, water and arable land in a network of hexagons within the functional urban areas of three European Capitals: Prague, Vienna, and Budapest. The results reveal that areas with relatively higher levels of LULCO are observed in Prague, particularly in its southern part, with slightly reduced levels in Budapest. Conversely, Vienna's functional urban area exhibits lower LULCO values, especially in its northern part. The calculated spatial distribution of local spatial optimality - LULCO shows trends consistent with the Shannon index of heterogeneity. However, the approach used provides additional information on the relative degree of equilibrium between the selected land use and land cover types and is significantly more sensitive to small changes in the optimality of their representation. The method employed in this study is an autonomous stochastic model grounded in the structure of linear games in normal form. It facilitates the calculation of the distribution of Nash equilibrium probabilities within data represented by spatial cases characterized by multiple attributes. This approach offers a novel perspective, applicable to various environmental data in different contexts.

Keywords: Functional urban areas, Optimality, Nash equilibrium, Heterogeneity, Land use assessment, Urban sustainability

1. Introduction

Climate change, demographic dynamics, rapid urbanization, and associated land use changes have been closely intertwined with the sustainability of European urban landscapes (Schiavina et al., 2022). The European context is characterized by lower demographic growth and more dispersed built-up patterns compared to other world regions, particularly in the early 2000s (Alvarez et al., 2021; Florczyk et al., 2019; Vollset et al., 2020). Seventy-five percent of Europe's population lives in urban areas, including cities, towns, and suburbs (European Environment Agency, 2020). Although the urban population of Europe is expected to increase to approximately 83.7% in 2050 (European Commission, 2020), the research found that European urban areas increase even at a faster pace than the population and expand in areas where the population declines (Schiavina et al., 2022).

Urban land expansion and related land use changes have large impacts on the environment, in particular on agricultural land, forests, and water (Breuste et al., 2015; Cimini et al., 2023; Haase, Frantzeskaki, et al., 2014). Once a city is built, its physical form and land use patterns can be locked in for generations. In this way, research on urban sustainability highlights the importance of equilibrium between different land uses in urban areas (Haase, Larondelle, et al., 2014; Votsis & Haavisto, 2019; Zhang et al., 2019). A well-considered and integrated land use mix is fundamental to achieving sustainable urban development and supporting a range of different ecosystem services and human activities (Ma & Wen, 2021). This land use mix approach is a cornerstone of effective land use policy (Zhuo et al., 2022), as it provides a robust framework for creating vibrant, walkable and transit-oriented neighborhoods that offer a rich spectrum of opportunities for people to live, work and engage in leisure activities within close proximity (Gehrke & Clifton 2016; Pauleit et al., 2005). It can create a sense of community and belonging and contribute to the overall stability and vibrancy of the area.

This study applies an approach guided by Vach (2020), using selected principles of game theory to compute the spatial distribution of the probability of the Nash equilibrium (NE) (Nash, 1950). The

Nash equilibrium is a concept in game theory that refers to a stable state in which no player has an incentive to change their strategy, given the strategies of the other players. Here in the context of land use and land cover (LULC), NE is used to describe a situation in which different LULCs are in balance, and no one LULC has an advantage over the others. NE between LULCs contributes to local LULC equilibrium by ensuring that each LULC is being used at an optimal level, i.e., not being overused or underused, which can help to prevent imbalances or conflicts between different uses (covers) (Sharp & Whittaker, 2003). When LULCs are in equilibrium, it can provide a stable foundation for planning and policy decisions, as it indicates that the current mix of LULCs is meeting the needs of the community (Correia & Mascarenhas, 1999).

The probability of reaching NE in this context represents the degree of spatial optimality of the representation of the selected land use and land cover types (LULCO). The highest LULCO values are achieved in locations where the individual LULCs are each represented to the maximum extent compared to other locations. Importantly, LULCO does not imply equal representation of all LULCs (as would be the case with the highest Shannon entropy), but rather the most beneficial and spatially optimal configuration. Nonetheless, the spatial distribution of LULCO tends to resemble patterns seen in the Shannon heterogeneity index, without showing markedly distinct trends.

The research problem of landscape structure evaluation is topical (Decker et al., 2017; Jongman, 2002; Prokopová et al., 2019). It is often based on the landscape structure corresponding to a set of individual landscape units (LUs) connected in a landscape network (Bonacini et al., 2017). Graph theory is an effective tool for inferring the spatial structure of LUs connectivity (Urban et al., 2009). Changes in selected landscape parameters and their equilibrium and stability can be deterministically modeled using specific systems of differential equations (Bonacini et al., 2017; Gobattoni et al., 2012). In addition, discrete models use Markov chains (B.-L. Li, 1995; Yemshanov & Perera, 2002). In practical applications, complex approaches combining multiple primary methods are also used in modeling landscape change and assessing landscape equilibrium and connectivity (Gobattoni et al.,

2011; Pelorosso et al., 2011, 2017). An overview of performance-based approaches to urban planning modeling is provided by Pelorosso (2020). Additionally, the problem is also the very definition of what a measure of local equilibrium is supposed to represent and from what it is supposed to be derived (Grimm & Wissel, 1997; Perry, 2002; Turner et al., 1993). Starting points used to address these questions include the concept of entropy and information theory (Vranken et al., 2014). The presented approach is a mathematically robust stochastic model (Vach, 2020) derived based on general assumptions of the structure of linear games and the concept of NE. In terms of the type of results, the stochastic model used can be categorized as a multi-objective optimization (MOO) approach, which is reviewed by e.g., Petchrompo et al. (2022). This paper aims to evaluate the spatial distribution of the probability of NE interpreted as LULCO. In other words, we aim to analyze the local optimality rate between different types of LULC in the functional urban areas (FUA) of three European Capitals: Prague, Vienna, and Budapest in the territories defined in the Urban Atlas, Copernicus Land Monitoring Service (UA2012). The Capitals represent typical European cities as they are dense and diverse, consisting of a medieval core and mixed-use neighborhoods. They are similar in population (Prague 1.2 million, Vienna and Budapest both around 1.7 million) and geographical location in central Europe. The Capitals have, however, followed different historical paths. Austria developed into a neutral center between the West and the East. Hungary and the Czechoslovakia were part of the Eastern Bloc from 1948 to 1989. As members of the former Council for Mutual Economic Assistance (so-called Comecon), the Czechoslovakia and Hungary shared a common ideology and resources under the complete governmental control of the Soviet Union (Czechoslovakia ceases to exist in 1992 - the Czech Republic and Slovak Republic are established as independent states). These geopolitical developments significantly impacted LULC management across the three cities.

This paper primarily uses LULCO to evaluate the spatial optimality of the representation of green and water areas in FUAs, divided into hexagonal units of 8.4 km². The analysis results in a spatial

distribution of the maximum representation rate of four LULC types: forests; grasslands and other green areas; water and wetlands; and arable land and permanent crops. In this context, areas with a higher proportion of green and water cover, that indicate a higher probability of NE, inferred from the specific pattern of permutations of LULC representation across all hexagons defined in the three FUAs. These permutations are conceptualized as linear games, where the four LULC types act as players. In addition, the spatial distribution of LULCO is also evaluated for a fifth LULC category: non-green anthropogenic areas. This distribution is assessed against the Shannon entropy to assess how LULCO's optimality-based distribution aligns with more traditional measures of spatial heterogeneity.

This study explores four research questions that are reflected in the structure of the methods and results sections. The questions are:

(RQ1) What are the differences in the spatial distribution of LULCO of green and water areas between the study functional urban areas?

(RQ2) Considering average LULCO of green and water areas as a function of distance from a city center, what are the differences between the Capitals?

(RQ3) How do even seemingly small changes in LULC of green and water areas in FUAs show up in the exact quantified LULCO values?

(RQ4) How does the spatial distribution of LULCO compare with the normalized Shannon index of LULC heterogeneity in the FUAs studied?

2. Methods

2.1 Empirical approach

The concept of using the structure of linear games in normal form to evaluate the equilibrium distribution in data represented by spatial cases with multiple characteristics was proposed in a

general context in Vach (2020). This approach employs the stochastic application of linear game theory, where payoff tables are continually generated through permutations based on spatial datasets.

In this study, the approach is newly applied to data representing LULC characteristics in specific localized contexts. In these cases, LULC data are defined by dividing the assessed maps of three FUA by a hexagonal grid at a selected scale, thereby defining spatial cases: hexagons with different representations of LULC types. From these cases, as elements representing vectors of numerical values of LULC representation, payoff tables of linear games can then be generated by permutations (vectors of representation values are taken as payoff vectors). These tables form multidimensional symmetric arrays whose dimensions are defined by the number of LULC types included. For example, for finding the optimum in the representation of three LULC types (forest, pastures, water), it is a cubic array whose edge can be formed by two or more cases (2^3 , 3^3 ... cases). Regardless of the specific payoff values (here formed by the representation of LULC in each case - hexagon), arrays created in this way can always be considered as games with NE in pure or mixed strategies (Nash 1951). However this approach does not define the information content of the primary strategies leading to payoff arrays created by permutations. Nevertheless, even strategies without information content, which can be considered stochastic, still represent individual LULC types (e.g., forest, pastures, water). These can be interpreted as interacting entities, or 'players' in this sense.

The lack of information about the strategies in the game does not preclude the possibility of identifying NE in the game array. If an equilibrium is found in pure strategies, it corresponds to the intersection of specific rows and columns in the payoff array – that is, a specific case (hexagon) where the vector of LULC type representation takes on values representing the most advantageous compromise for these LULC types as players in the game.

For this case (hexagon), the identified NE is counted within the currently permuted game array. Each case (hexagon) is continuously evaluated in all game arrays that can be permutationally generated

from all cases defined in the three FUAs. The resulting probability of NE for a given hexagon is calculated as the ratio of the number of games in which that hexagon appears as NE to the total number of permutation-generated games in which it is included.

The mathematical foundations of the described approach are detailed in Vach (2020). In the context of this application study, it is important to note that the resulting spatial distribution of NE probability is derived from a mathematically justified permutation structure designed to ensure maximum statistical significance. This permutation structure is defined to provide the result with the maximal statistical significance. Thus, the games generated are those with the highest number, which are symmetric game arrays with the same number of stochastic strategies for all players – LULC types. The number of stochastic strategies for each player - the LULC type is set to the lowest possible value in this study, namely two representing the lowest computational complexity. That is, NE is sought in multidimensional symmetric game arrays with 2^n elements (cases – hexagons), where n is the number of players (four or five LULC types) determining the spatial dimension of the arrays. While larger input case numbers could potentially generate game configurations with more than two formal strategies for interacting entities, these alternatives may not be considered in the implemented application (e.g., four players, each with six stochastic strategies - then one game array represents $6^4 = 1296$ cases; for five players, a similar number of cases would allow the construction of an array with four strategies for each - $4^5 = 1024$ cases, etc.). This is because they do not alter the overall trend of the NE probability distribution but merely accentuate it compared to the simplest variant with two formal strategies. Thus, the resulting spatial distribution of NE probability, based on game arrays with two strategies per LULC type, effectively captures the same trends as would be revealed by a single, large permutation-based game array containing all evaluated hexagons.

For completeness, it should also be noted that NE is only sought in pure (stochastic) strategies in the permuted game arrays. NE emerging in mixed strategies are not included in the spatial probability

distribution statistics, as they do not significantly impact the overall trend, which is most evident in multidimensional game arrays (three or more players), as demonstrated in Vach (2020). The detailed step-by-step process of computing the spatial distribution of NE probability in the context of LULC data evaluation is shown in the flow chart in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Scheme of calculation of the probability of NE in one of the defined squares. The resulting NE probability for the evaluated square is the sum of the increments obtained by effective permutations of all game arrays that can be formed as a combination of m cases (hexagons) from all defined cases (hexagons) in the three FUAs evaluated. Adapted from Vach (2000).

In summary, the proposed approach exhibits the following essential characteristics:

Permutation-generated game arrays are payoff tables of constant-sum games (convertible to zero-sum games). That is, the case (hexagon) in which the strategies representing NE intersect exhibit Pareto optimal (PO) representation of LULC types. The resulting spatial distribution of NE probability (which generally relates to strategies in permuted games) is identical to the spatial distribution of PO

probability, which, however, already relates to individual cases (hexagons) and not to stochastic strategies without information content. The approach thus uses the basic principles of game theory to derive the probability with which a given case (hexagon) is close to the point of absolute optimality on the multidimensional Pareto front. This absolute optimality represents the NE probability is equal to one, i.e., NE in a given case is found in all permuted games. Such a hexagon is unlikely to be identified. The resulting spatial distribution of the degree of optimality of LULC types (i.e., LULCO) should, therefore, be interpreted as relative - the hexagon with the highest LULCO value can be considered as lying closest to the point of optimality on the Pareto front among all others from the three FUAs.

The model does not use any parametrization or specific settings and is generally applicable to any spatial data allowing the definition of local cases with a different representation of the evaluated characteristics; it is by no means only a land use and land cover type of data. The method has already been applied to the problem of optimizing the restoration of postmining land areas (Vach et al., 2021).

2.2 The analysis of LULCO

The spatial distribution of the probability of NE interpreted as LULCO in the land use and land cover of the three functional urban areas is assessed based on five essential LULC types: forests, pastures, and other green areas, water and wetlands, arable land and permanent crops, urban fabric, industrial, and other anthropogenic areas. The individual cases from which the permuted game configurations are generated are defined via a hexagonal grid covering the LULC evaluation FUAs maps (border hexagons are considered cases if they do not contain more than 20% of the empty territory). This approach is based on the evaluation of the absolute areal representation of the specified aforementioned LULC types within each of the hexagons, i.e. the cases defined together in

all three FUAs. The observed total areas of the evaluated LULC characteristics within a hexagon serve as the basis for generating payoff values, which in turn represent an element of the symmetric array, also known as the permuted game array.

By RQ1 - RQ3, the spatial optimality of green and water areas is evaluated. In this case, the absolute representations of the four LULC types - forests, pastures, water, and arable land in each hexagon (i.e., case) are taken as payoff values. Each permuted game array is then four-dimensional - corresponding to the four interacting LULC types as players. Cases are defined by hexagons with edge lengths of 1.8 km and an area of 8.4 km², representing 2275 evaluated cases in the three FUAs combined. The computation of NE in the permuted four-dimensional game arrays is performed in parallel - on one CPU for each of the 2275 cases. Examination of all game arrays in which each case may occur represented an average of 24 h. Thus, 2275 CPU days were consumed to evaluate green and water areas LULCO in the three FUAs.

The analysis corresponding to RQ4 evaluates the spatial optimality of all five essential LULCs, including urban fabric, industrial, and other anthropogenic areas. Therefore, this is not an evaluation of the optimal representation of green and water areas (as in RQ1 - RQ3) but a comparison of the optimality of the representation of essential LULC types with Shannon entropy - heterogeneity in grid hexagons. All areas in each hexagon where the sum of the relative representation of all LULCs is equal to one are evaluated, which is in accordance with the definition of the Shannon index.

Evaluating the degree of optimality of the representation of five entities - LULC types is computationally demanding. NE is searched for in five-dimensional permuted game arrays, and the solution for one hexagon case requires approximately 55–75 hours (on one CPU). Therefore, the hexagon grid for this task is less dense than in case with four entities, resulting in a smaller total number of hexagon cases - 585 across the three FUAs combined. The evaluation represented about 1600 CPU days. The edge length of the hexagons is 3.5 km and the area is 31.8 km².

Shannon entropy – the heterogeneity of five LULC, with which the evaluation of spatial optimality of LULC is compared, is calculated as a normalized index - efficiency η_k (in the hexagon – case k) according to the following equation:

$$\eta_k = - \sum_{i=1}^5 \frac{p_k(x_i) \log(p_k(x_i))}{\log(5)}$$

Where $p_k(x_i)$ is the relative representation of the i -th type of LULC in the hexagon – case k ($\sum p_k(x_i) = 1$).

2.3 Input data

The evaluation of the spatial distribution of LULCO of three functional urban areas is based on the data from Urban Atlas , Copernicus Land Monitoring Service (UA2012, UA2018). The primary input data is Urban Atlas Land Cover/Land Use 2012, which has a validated status and is used to address research questions RQ1 - RQ4. To evaluate LULCO changes in the case of minor changes in the representation of LULC types (RQ3), Urban Atlas Land Cover/Land Use 2018, which is currently only partially validated, is used as a supplementary comparative data set. The reason for using this not fully validated data input to address RQ3 is that the validated Urban Atlas Land Cover/Land Use 2006 is defined in the territory for all three FUAs differently from 2012 and has a different LULC categorization. A direct comparison of LULC data from 2012 and 2006 would, therefore, be problematic. However, the purpose of RQ3 is to show the model sensitivity of LULCO to minor changes in the representation of LULC types in specifically selected cases - even though these changes may also be related to the inaccuracy of not fully validated data. It is not intended to systematically evaluate fundamental changes in LULC with demonstrable validity.

The data have been modified for the assessment. LULC types of pastures, herbaceous vegetation associations, green urban areas, and complex and mixed cultivation patterns were merged into the category of 'pastures and other green areas'. Wetlands are considered water and are part of the LULC type 'water and wetlands'. Annual and permanent crops were merged into the category of 'arable land'. The LULC type forests are used as they are in the input data - Urban Atlas Land Cover/Land Use. All sub-types of anthropogenic areas are combined into 'urban fabric, industrial, and other anthropogenic areas'. This modification of the input data, representing a reduction of the original 27 LULC types to five, is performed to evaluate LULCO using the concept used here. This reduction is performed with the aim of maximum adequacy but may be influenced by the subjective view of the authors. The final input data on LULC of FUAs of Prague, Vienna, and Budapest are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. The input land use and land cover data of functional urban areas in Prague, Vienna, and Budapest. Data are taken from Urban Atlas 2012 (UA2012).

3. Results

3.1 LULCO of green and water areas in functional urban areas of three Capitals

The resulting distribution of LULCO of green and water areas (by RQ1 - RQ3), evaluating the degree of spatial optimality of the representation of four LULC types - forests, pastures, and other green

areas, water and wetlands, and arable land - in the three FUAs is shown in Figure 3. As described in Chapter 2.2, spatial optimality (LULCO) is evaluated in a grid of hexagons with an edge length of 1.8 km, i.e., an area of 8.4 km². This selected size of the evaluated cases – hexagons - was suitable for obtaining results with informative values adequate to the approach used.

Figure 3. Spatial distribution of LULCO of green and water areas in functional urban areas of Prague, Vienna, and Budapest, state 2012.

The results show the following overall trends: The largest area with a high level of LULCO was identified in the southeast of Prague, as apparent across all variants presented in Figure 3 (values > 0.1). In contrast, low spatial optimality (LULCO) has been measured in the area north of Vienna with a relatively low representation of pastures and water areas (values < 0.05).

To allow an exact comparison of the three functional urban areas, the results shown in Figure 3 are presented in terms of the frequency of the calculated values in the quartiles defined between the received minimum and maximum LULCO values in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Frequency of LULCO of green and water areas values calculated on three FUAs in the quartiles defined between the received minimum and maximum.

The frequencies of occurrence of the calculated LULCO of green and water areas values in each quartile in Figure 4 show that the most significant degree of LULCO emerges for the functional urban area of Prague.

3.2 Average LULCO of green and water areas as a function of distance from a city center

The comparison of the evaluated FUAs in terms of the generalized spatial distribution of LULCO of green and water areas (corresponding to RQ2), which preserves horizontal directional symmetry, is performed by averaging its values depending on the distance from the centers of urban areas. The geometric centroids of the metropolitan regions defined in individual FUAs are considered centers. Individual sets of hexagons whose LULCO values are included in the current averaging are defined by the same distance of their centroids from the center of urban areas. The dependence of the quantified average LULCO on the distance from the urban centers is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Average LULCO of green and water areas as a function of distance from urban centers (which are defined as centroids of the metropolitan regions). The light red color in figures a–c represents the interval \pm standard deviation. Figure d compares the average LULCO values for all three FUAs.

This analysis is most favorable overall for the functional urban area of Prague. In detail, it is apparent that Vienna performs best in the central areas of cities - up to approximately 1.7 km from the center, where a large proportion of anthropogenic areas and LULCO of green and water areas are low. Further from the centers, Prague shows the highest values of averaged LULCO of green and water areas, with a maximum at a distance of 8–10 km, where the positive effect of urban greenery, forests, and water areas is more significant. For the FUAs Vienna and Budapest, these maxima are more distant (Vienna 12 km, Budapest 13 km) and less pronounced. From a distance of 15 km from city centers to about 20–22 km, LULCO of green and water areas show an upward trend for all three

FUA, with the maximum for Budapest at 20 km exceeding LULCO Prague. From a distance of 30–32 km, on the other hand, a decline in LULCO is evident for all three FUA.

However, it should be added that the sets of LULCO values symmetrically distributed at increasing distances from the centroids of the metropolitan regions show a practically uniform distribution from approximately 6 to 8 km, which is documented by relatively higher values of standard deviations – see Figures a - c. Therefore, it is impossible to identify LULCO values typically occurring at particular larger (6 - 8 km) distances. Respectively, the LULCO parameter is highly sensitive to the specific representation of individual LULCs.

3.3 Change in LULC between 2012 and 2018 and its impact on LULCO of green and water areas

As mentioned in Chapter 2.3, the evaluation of LULC changes is based on comparing the situation of three FUAs in 2012 and 2018. The results presented in connection with RQ3 only show the model LULCO quantification of even small changes in LULC. Given the only partial validation of the Urban Atlas Land Cover/Land Use 2018 data, it cannot be fully guaranteed that the examples presented always represent temporal changes in the real landscape.

This temporal comparison allows the spatial identification of specific changes in LULCO of green and water areas which may be significant for land use and land cover management and environmental impact assessment practices. The method used directly quantifies (in absolute terms - in LULCO values, see Figure 6, or in relative terms - in percentage changes in LULCO, see Figure 7) the impacts of LULC changes between 2012 and 2018 on LUCO of green and water areas. The examples selected in Figure 6 and 7 show the exact impact of specific LULC changes.

Changes in LULCO - 2018 compared to 2012

Figure 6. Changes in the spatial distribution of LULCO of green and water areas in FUAs of Prague, Vienna, and Budapest, 2018 compared to 2012. Changes in LULCO are expressed in absolute values. Arrows indicate specific LULC changes leading to different LULCO in the presented hexagons for 2018.

Figure 7 shows the differences between LULCO 2018 and 2012, which are relativized as percentages of 2012. Therefore, the resulting spatial distribution of the significance of each local change differs from Figure 6, which presents these differences in absolute terms. Figure 7 reflects the significance of each change in terms of 2012 status. The change that appears relatively small in absolute terms may be significant relative to a lower LULCO value in 2012.

Changes in LULCO - 2018 compared to 2012, relative values as a percentage of the 2012 situation

Figure 7. Changes in the spatial distribution of LULCO in FUAs of Prague, Vienna, and Budapest, in 2018 compared to 2012. The values are expressed as percent change of LULCO of green and water areas from 2012. Arrows indicate specific LULC changes leading to different LULCO (in percentages of 2012) in the presented hexagons for 2018.

Figures 6 and 7 show that a significant change of LULCO may be represented by a relatively small and seemingly insignificant difference in the occurrence of a LULC type that is less represented in selected hexagons. The chosen examples demonstrate the exact impact of specific LULC changes of LULCO.

The examples presented in the hexagons in Figures 6 and 7 can be interpreted as follows:

For Figure 6:

P1 - A minor increase in water areas and pastures in 2018 compared to 2012 represents a relatively significant increase in the spatial optimality of the representation of four types of LULC (reflecting green and water areas) - the LULCO of green and water areas value.

P2 - The expansion of the share of anthropogenic areas at the expense of green areas represents a significant decrease in LULCO.

V1 - The conversion of arable land, which predominates in the 2012 situation, to pastures, whose share is more significant in the 2018 situation, increases the LULCO value.

V2 - The loss of relatively small water areas (and also arable land) associated with increased anthropogenic areas means a significant decrease in LULCO.

B1 - An increase in the proportion of forest in an area covered mainly by arable land significantly positively affects the LULCO value.

B2 - LULC shows greater heterogeneity of green and water areas, but the decline in the proportion of relatively less represented pastures will significantly affect the decrease in LULCO.

For Figure 7:

P1 - The effect of an increase in the proportion of pastures from a very low level to a significantly higher level represents a 30% increase in LULCO value in 2018 compared to 2012.

P2 - A more significant elimination of pastures, albeit related to an increase in forest area (which is replaced by anthropogenic area elsewhere), leads to a decrease in LULCO of approximately 40%.

V1 - In areas where pastures are practically not represented, even a slight increase in their share is significant for a positive change in LULCO (by approximately 30%).

V2 - An increase in anthropogenic areas at the expense of green areas represents a 10% decrease in LULCO (of green and water areas).

B1 - Similar to V1, here, there is a slight increase in the proportion of forest, leading to a 35% increase in LULCO.

B2 - Replacing a significant portion of pastures with forests and increasing the share of anthropogenic areas at the expense of arable land leads to a 35% decrease in LULCO.

3.4 LULCO of all five defined LULC types compared to the normalized Shannon entropy index

Spatial optimality - LULCO of all five defined LULC types, including anthropogenic areas, was evaluated by RQ4. For direct comparison with the normalized Shannon entropy index - heterogeneity, evaluating the spatial optimality for the entire area of the defined hexagons (cases) was useful. The sum of the relative proportions of the individual LULC types was then equal to one in each hexagon. When calculating LULCO, NE was sought in permuted five-dimensional game arrays - in games of five LULC types as interacting entities - players.

As mentioned in Chapter 2.2, calculating the optimality for five types of LULC as interacting entities is computationally demanding and, therefore, could not be carried out in the same detail as the optimality solution for green and water areas evaluating four types of LULC. The evaluation of the optimality of the representation of the five LULC types was, therefore, still feasible in a grid of hexagons with an edge length of 3.5 km and an area of 31.8 km² (requiring a computing capacity of approximately 1600 CPU days). The results, including the comparative spatial distribution of the normalized Shannon index, are shown for the three evaluated FUAs in Figure 8 a, b.

a Forests vs. Pastures vs. Water vs. Arable land vs. Anthropogenic areas
Hexagons with edge length 3.5 km (cases)

b Forests + Pastures + Water + Arable land + Anthropogenic areas
Hexagons with edge length 3.5 km (cases)

Figure 8. Comparison of LULCO spatial distribution and Shannon index in FUA of Prague, Vienna, and Budapest, state 2012.

a) LULCO spatial distribution reflecting the optimality of representation of all five LULC types, including anthropogenic areas.

b) Normalized Shannon entropy (heterogeneity) index of representation of all five LULC types included.

The resulting spatial distribution of the overall optimality (LULCO) of the representation of all five defined LULC types – see Figure 8 a – is not significantly different from the distribution of LULCO for green and water areas (see Figure 3). Even with the inclusion of anthropogenic areas, higher LULCO values are found in the southeast direction of Prague and, conversely, lower values north of Vienna.

The spatial distribution of the normalized Shannon heterogeneity index in the three evaluated FUAs (see Figure 8b) shows similar trends to LULCO (Figure 8a). However, the Shannon index shows a significantly higher proportion of hexagons - green cases showing values close to the maximum (value one). This fact is related to the fundamentally different definitions of the two characteristics.

The theoretical maximum value of LULCO represents the ideal point of optimality on the Pareto front, i.e., a case (hexagon) of representation of individual LULC types that is more advantageous for absolutely all of these LULC types (here are five types) than all other cases of representation. This does not have to be the same proportion of all LULC types, as is the case with the maximum value of the normalized Shannon index. The condition of high optimality - LULCO close to one - is, therefore, much stricter than the condition of equal proportions for the maximum Shannon index.

LULCO evaluates the degree of optimality, while the Shannon index evaluates the degree of entropy - heterogeneity. These are fundamentally different characteristics, but their comparison (Figure 8) is intended to demonstrate that LULCO, a newly proposed approach to urban (and other) landscape evaluation, provides meaningful results whose trends are not inconsistent with the standard established characteristic - the Shannon index.

4. Discussion

4.1 Model accuracy and the interpretation of the results

The outcome of this research provides insights into the spatial arrangement of LULCO. This spatial optimality is measured by the probability of a Nash equilibrium among four or five defined land use and land cover types within three functional urban areas in Central Europe. The interpretation and importance of this finding become clearer within the framework of multi-objective optimization (MOO) methods. These methodologies enable the calculation of optimal compromises in situations involving multiple conflicting objectives. Their results are generally similar to those of LULCO presented in this study. MOO methods are used to solve many optimization problems, as shown by numerous literature review papers (Branke et al., 2008; Meignan et al., 2015; Petchrompo et al., 2022; Wątróbski et al., 2019; Yenisey & Yagmahan, 2014). Several works analyzed in the review

by Rahman & Szabo (2021) deal directly with multi-objective urban land use optimization, most often focused on maximizing spatial compactness, maximizing land use compatibility, and maximizing land use suitability.

The conventional outcome of the MOO methods consists of a collection of trade-off instances that illustrate Pareto optimality (PO). This condition arises when no objective factors can be strengthened without weakening another. The results of this study can be viewed as a spatial distribution of the degree of optimality in terms of the assessed LULC types as opposing factors. Whether our approach is a variation of the many MOO methods or simulates interactions of entities (in this study, LULC types as interacting entities) can be addressed by assessing its structure against specific MOO approaches. Modern a posteriori MOO approaches, relevant for this comparison, frequently use genetic algorithms to identify trade-offs along the Pareto front. An overview is given by, for example, Konak et al. (2006) and von Lücken et al. (2014). In terms of the choice of the most optimal alternatives from the array of Pareto optimal solutions achieved. In this context, game theory assumptions, particularly the concept of Nash equilibria, often come into play (Cao et al., 2020). The concept of NE can also be employed across the entire procedure of addressing the MOO challenge by employing a hybrid genetic algorithm that seeks out Nash equilibria (X. Li et al., 2012; Xiao et al., 2015). A comprehensive overview of endeavors merging MOO and game theory can be found in the work of Sohrabi & Azgomi (2018).

The structure of the stochastic model employed in this study deviates from the MOO methodologies. It does not rely on a deliberate search for cases (hexagons) with optimal trade-offs among the included LULC types. The goal is not to solve an optimization problem but to equally assess all-encompassed cases and assign them probability values defining the extent to which they are at the optimal point of the Pareto front. The outcome of this study therefore holds equal significance for every case. Consequently, this approach renders the use of evolutionary optimization algorithms and similar methods unnecessary. The sole overarching evaluation tool employed in this approach is the

Nash equilibrium. The essence of the approach is the specific permutation generation of configurations of linear games, which is justified in its detailed description by author (Vach, 2020). In this regard, the proposed approach is entirely innovative. It is worth noting that the approach yields outcomes representing Nash equilibrium probability (interpreted as a measure of optimality - LULCO) values for each case. These values are computed directly, obviating the need to search and select them along the Pareto front or similar avenues. In the context of this purely game structure, where the proposed approach reflects the observed state due to potential competitive interactions realized within the corresponding set of possible linear games, the approach effectively functions as an interaction model.

The presented approach introduces an autonomous stochastic model of system interactions. Notably, the model is efficient and well practicable, particularly in environmental applications. Its versatility is evident in its ability to process diverse spatial datasets. The derived NE probability values possess the capability to extend beyond LUCO, finding relevance in various ecosystem contexts. While acknowledging that computational complexity escalates with the inclusion of characteristics (interacting entities) and cases, the model's mathematical structure dictates a minimal case count requirement of 2^n for n characteristics. Nonetheless, the calculation is consistently parallelizable, and for standard input data scales akin to the task described in this paper, computations (using the capabilities of the grid cluster) remain feasible and conclude within a reasonable timeframe - typically spanning tens of hours.

4.2 LULCO versus Shannon index

The concept of landscape equilibrium is reflected in the literature mainly in the context of the spatiotemporal response of landscapes to disturbance (Turner et al., 1993; He & Mladenoff, 1999), morphological equilibrium in terms of soil formation (Heimsath et al., 1997, 2001), etc.

However, the exact calculation of the LULCO used here, based on LULC types representation and the concept of spatial distribution of NE probability, is an entirely new and previously unestablished type of evaluation.

The obtained NE probability values express a measure of the optimality of the representation of the evaluated LULC types - LULCO. The highest values come out in cases with relatively most significant areas of each evaluated LULC type compared to their areas in other cases. Therefore, the LULCO values are based on comparisons between cases - hexagons (but using specific mathematically justified permuted structures - games).

Land use and land cover in environmental and ecological contexts is often evaluated in terms of its heterogeneity using the Shannon index (Stein & Kreft, 2014). Altieri et al. (2018) used a rigorous spatial entropy-based approach to measure urban sprawl associated with the diffusion of metropolitan cities. Shannon index evaluates the degree of entropy, with the highest values corresponding to cases with the most even representation of each LULC type. Compared to the LULCO calculation used here, this is a fundamentally different concept, as individual cases are evaluated in isolation, and the resulting value of the Shannon index is in no way related to how cases compare to each other.

However, a comparison of the LULCO and heterogeneity (normalized Shannon index) calculation results for all five defined LULC types - see Figure 8 a and b shows an explicit agreement between the obtained trends. This correspondence is logical. Cases with a more even representation of LULC types (with a higher value of the normalized Shannon index) also show a higher LULCO because they represent a higher degree of optimality compared to the others. On the other hand, a comparison of Figures 8 a and b shows an obvious difference in the sensitivity of the two concepts to smaller changes in optimality. For all three functional urban areas, higher values of heterogeneity (Shannon index 0.8, etc.) emerge even in cases where the obtained LULCO values are only at around 20 - 30% of the optimal maximum.

Thus, it can be summarized that the exact evaluation of the LULCO presented here has an informational value and an environmental and possibly ecological significance comparable to the Shannon index of heterogeneity in the context of the obtained trend. If, in addition to heterogeneity, the locations with the highest degree of optimality, i.e., the cases with the most optimal area representation of each LULC type compared to the others, are to be identified practically, the NE probability evaluation-based concept used here is more sensitive and accurate than the Shannon index. This fact is related to the fact that the existence of NE is conditioned by the specific and unique situation in the structure of strategies and payoffs in the linear game.

4.3 LULCO in three European Capitals

The issue of land use and land cover and its changes in urban areas has been documented by authors who analyzed spatiotemporal changes in LULC, using data from the European Environment Agency's Urban Atlas, Copernicus Land Monitoring Service (e.g., Aksoy et al., 2022; Grešlová et al., 2023; Noszczyk et al., 2022; Pazúr et al., 2017; Starczewski et al., 2023; Wnęk et al., 2021). In addition, there are analyses of changes in green infrastructure connectivity (Wang et al., 2022), classification of urban structure using landscape cover and cluster analysis (Kukulska-Kozieł et al., 2019), studies of landscape characteristics of suburban forests (Salvati et al., 2017), and synthesis of available land use and land cover data of different types (Rosina et al., 2018). Using a hexagonal tessellation, Kudas et al. (2024) evaluated temporal changes in spatial diversity in land use and land cover in four central European capitals (Prague, Warsaw, Bratislava, and Budapest).

In our analysis, we directly address the question of quantifying the degree of optimality represented by LULC of the functional urban areas of three Capitals in central Europe. Our primary finding is the quantified spatial distribution of LULCO among the primary LULC types.

Our findings underscore the significant role of water bodies and wetlands in LULCO of urban areas. The LULCO values obtained are particularly sensitive to the presence of water bodies, which are the least represented LULC type. Our analysis confirms the critical role of water in the landscape as a factor of local optimality, a role that gains even more importance in the context of climate change. Furthermore, our analysis enables the precise quantification of LULC changes, allowing us to measure the exact impact, such as the local expansion of anthropogenic areas at the expense of forests or pastures etc.

4.4 Limitations

The resulting spatial distribution of NE probability serves as a measure of the LULCO among the assessed LULC types of the three functional urban areas under evaluation. However, it is important to clarify that this optimality, in this context, is solely derived from the representation of the LULC types within the selected hexagonal elements of the spatial grid. We recognize that the ecological optimality or equilibrium of the landscapes is inherently more complex. Factors such as the specific spatial structure, connectivity of landscape elements, and the presence of other non-negligible landscape types all play significant roles. Therefore, the presented results should be viewed as modeled values, shaped by the constraints and limitations of the input data used in this study. For instance, if additional, more specific landscape types were to be incorporated into the calculation, the resulting trend in local landscape optimality for the three functional urban areas evaluated might exhibit variations.

5. Conclusions

The spatial distribution of LULCO based on the probability of Nash equilibrium calculations in the LULC of three functional urban areas of Prague, Vienna, and Budapest represents a novel outcome. It provides insights into the local equilibrium among four (representing green and water areas) or

fiveLUC types and offers a novel approach to measure the local optimality of these urban land uses and land cover.

The computation was performed through an approach that leverages the framework of linear games in normal form. This method was employed to assess the distribution of NE probabilities within spatial datasets characterized by multiple attributes. It utilizes a self-contained stochastic model designed for environmental applications (Vach, 2020). Notably, this approach is strictly general, does not use any application parameterization and demonstrates a commendable degree of robustness. Information on the spatial distribution of LULCO represents environmental and ecological significance comparable to the Shannon heterogeneity index. Still, it is significantly more sensitive to small LULC types representation optimality changes, which have been proven for the evaluation of LULCO green and water areas. This sensitivity can then be used effectively to assess LULC changes accurately over time.

The results show that comparatively higher levels of LULCO (of green and water areas and all five defined LULC types) are evident in the functional urban area of Prague, particularly in its southern region. There is a slight reduction in LULCO observed for Budapest, and lower degree of LULCO is observed in Vienna, especially in its northern part. Therefore, the decline in LULCO, which was historically linked to the collectivization of agriculture and land consolidation during the 20th century (Lipský, 1995), is not presently apparent in the assessed functional urban areas.

Spatial optimality - LULCO is a parameter sensitive to changes in the representation of LULC types.

The observed local alterations, which are substantiated by discernible increases or decreases in LULCO, are characterized by sometimes relatively small shifts in the occurrence of LULC types.

The principal significance of both the results and the method lies in the acquisition of quantified information regarding the spatial distribution of LULCO (of green and water areas and all five defined LULC types) across larger spatial units. Equally significant is the universal applicability of the

employed approach, making it a valuable tool across various scenarios and settings. Measuring the LULCO between different LULC types in an urban area can help to understand how land is being used and how it could be used more effectively. It can help to inform land use and cover planning and policy decisions by providing a more accurate understanding of how land is being used, how it could be used more effectively, and where are any imbalances or disparities. This knowledge can reduce negative impacts on the environment and quality of life in the area (Pazúr et al., 2017; Schetke & Haase, 2008). For example, if LULCO is high for certain LULC in certain areas, it may indicate that those uses are well-suited to those locations and that additional development in those areas would be beneficial. On the other hand, if LULCO is low for certain land uses in certain areas, it may indicate that those uses are not well-suited to those locations and that alternative uses or development strategies should be considered.

Research on the optimality between different LULC in functional urban areas is an important area of study in the fields of LULC planning, urban studies, and environmental science. Further research can help to understand the complex interactions between different LULC and the impacts of urbanization on natural resources. It can also provide insights into strategies for managing and conserving these resources in the face of increasing urbanization. Future research agenda may involve collaboration with stakeholders, such as local governments, community organizations, and landowners, to understand the social and economic factors that influence land use and cover patterns in urban areas. By shedding light on the optimality between different LULC, this research can inform policies and practices promoting the sustainable use and management of natural resources in urban environments.

Acknowledgements

Computational resources were provided by the e-INFRA CZ project (ID:90254), supported by the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports of the Czech Republic.

Funding

This research has been supported by the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports of the Czech Republic (grant AdAgriF - Advanced methods of greenhouse gases emission reduction and sequestration in agriculture and forest landscape for climate change mitigation (CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004635)).

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Marek Vach: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Methodology, Resources, Software, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft.

Kamila Svobodova: Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Supervision, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing.

Data and codes availability statement

A dataset including land use data inputs, specifically formatted temporal input and output files from computing the spatial distribution of NE probability (interpreted as LULCO), and codes including computational Fortran code and auxiliary codes for data conversion are available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16094950> (Vach and Svobodova, 2025). The complete Fortran code set justifying the concept and its structure is available at <https://github.com/vachm/equsis>. A detailed description is formulated in (Vach, 2020), and for limited calculations (up to 32 dedicated cases and a maximum of 5 interacting entities), the website <http://equsis.com> is available.

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